

Modeling Fire Risk in Hawai'i Using Satellite, Atmospheric and Geographic Data

by

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Abstract

Wildfires threaten ecosystems, communities, and property, underscoring the need for accurate predictive models for disaster management. This project develops a Deep Neural Network (DNN) to estimate wildfire occurrence probability by integrating meteorological data, satellite fire detection records, and static environmental features like topography and vegetation classifications.

Using data since 2011, the model builds a sample from each satellite pixel, using meteorological, topographical, and fuel conditions as features and fire presence as the label. Temporal aggregation captures historical trends through averaged meteorological features. The DNN optimizes predictions using cross-entropy loss, producing spatial risk maps to support emergency planning and land management.

This research highlights machine learning's potential in wildfire prediction, offering a framework for integrating environmental data to mitigate fire risks and address global challenges.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Motivation

On the morning of August 8th, 2023, a fire ignited near Lahaina, Maui, resulting in the deadliest fire in the U.S. in over a century. The incident claimed 102 lives and caused an estimated \$5.5 billion in damages to rebuild, as reported by Maui County. The tragedy has sparked debates about accountability, but it underscores a critical issue: stakeholders lacked an understanding of the risk posed by fire ignition in close proximity to their community.

Figure 1.1: Estimated costs of the Lahaina Fire, as reported by Maui County.

Large-scale weather conditions during the event included a high-pressure region northeast of Maui and Hurricane Dora to the south, creating strong east-to-west winds that drove a downslope windstorm along Maui's leeward slopes [5]. Wildfires are low-probability but high-impact events. It is essential for stakeholders to understand how

real-time weather changes affect fire ignition probabilities to effectively allocate fire-fighting resources and implement preventive measures.

In response to the Lahaina tragedy, Maui County has installed three Remote Automatic Weather Stations (RAWS) and plans to deploy dozens of new Beta wildfire sensors developed by N5 Sensors Inc. in collaboration with federal agencies [1]. While this marks progress, additional data sources, such as Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS), offer untapped potential to better understand fire occurrence probabilities.

1.2 Background

Hawai'i's ecological diversity is among the highest in the world, but its unique ecosystems are highly susceptible to wildfires. Contributing factors include invasive species, prolonged droughts, and human activities [3]. Hawai'i's geographic isolation amplifies logistical and cost challenges for traditional data collection methods, such as deploying ground-based sensors or conducting aerial surveys. This isolation also limits access to the local expertise and resources needed for effective data analysis.

RS and GIS technologies have proven effective in spatiotemporal modeling and wildfire susceptibility mapping. Studies utilizing RS and GIS can be categorized into three primary methodologies [4]:

1. Physics-based methods: These simulate fire behavior using mathematical equations for heat transfer, combustion, and fluid dynamics.
2. Statistical methods: Techniques like GIS-based Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) assess fire occurrence probabilities by examining relationships between burned areas and conditioning factors.
3. Machine Learning (ML) methods: These data-driven approaches model non-linear relationships between fire occurrences and a diverse set of conditioning factors.

Wildfire conditioning factors are broadly classified as instantaneous or time-dependent. Instantaneous factors include anthropogenic, meteorological, and topographic features, where contributions to fire probability depend on observed values at a specific time. Time-dependent factors include fuel moisture (the water content in vegetation) and vegetation health, where contributions depend on rainfall patterns over preceding time periods.

This framework highlights the potential of combining instantaneous and time-dependent features to better understand and model fire occurrence probabilities, leveraging Hawai'i's unique geographic and ecological characteristics.

1.3 Objective

How can diverse data sources be utilized to estimate and map wildfire susceptibility on Hawai'i Island? This central research question guides the objectives of this project, which aims to address the unique environmental challenges and fire risks on the island.

The first step in achieving this goal is the development of a comprehensive fire inventory. This inventory serves as the foundation for understanding historical fire occurrences and patterns. Building upon this, the next objective is to collect and integrate diverse feature data, including meteorological conditions, topographical attributes, and fuel characteristics.

The data are then standardized and preprocessed to ensure compatibility with machine learning methods, forming a robust dataset suitable for model development. A predictive model is then constructed to estimate the probability of fire occurrence based on these features.

Finally, the model's outputs are used to create a wildfire susceptibility map for Hawai'i Island. This map provides a spatial visualization of fire risk, offering stakeholders a critical tool for informed decision-making regarding land management, resource allocation, and wildfire mitigation strategies.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Fire Domain Knowledge

Understanding the complex dynamics of wildfires is essential for effective prediction and management. Wildfires are influenced by a multitude of factors, including meteorological conditions (temperature, humidity, wind speed), topography (slope, aspect, elevation), vegetation types (fuel models), and human activities. In the context of Hawai'i Island and regions like Adana and Mersin provinces in Turkey, specific local factors such as invasive species, land use practices, and climatic variations play significant roles in fire occurrences.[4, 9] Knowledge of these factors allows for the development of more accurate wildfire susceptibility models that can inform prevention and mitigation strategies.

2.2 Advancements through Remote Sensing and GIS

Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) have revolutionized the field of wildfire study by providing sophisticated tools for data collection, analysis, and visualization. RS technologies enable the acquisition of real-time and high-resolution data over large and often inaccessible areas. Satellite imagery and aerial sensors capture critical information on land surface conditions, vegetation health, fuel moisture, and thermal anomalies indicative of active fires.

GIS serves as a powerful platform to integrate and analyze spatial data from various sources. By overlaying layers of environmental variables—such as topography, land cover, climate data, and historical fire occurrences—GIS facilitates the identification of patterns and high-risk zones. This integration is crucial for creating detailed wildfire susceptibility maps. For instance, the study conducted in Adana and Mersin provinces, Turkey, utilized RS and GIS to incorporate up-to-date land cover information and environmental variables into machine learning models, enhancing the accuracy of wildfire predictions [4].

On Hawai'i Island, the application of RS and GIS has been instrumental in capturing the unique environmental and ecological characteristics that influence wildfire sus-

ceptibility. The integration of these technologies allows for a comprehensive analysis of factors such as invasive grass species distribution, elevation-related climate variations, and human land use, which are critical for accurate modeling [9].

2.3 The Appropriateness of Machine Learning Methods

Machine Learning (ML) methods are particularly well-suited for wildfire susceptibility modeling due to their ability to handle complex, non-linear relationships among numerous variables. Wildfire occurrence is the result of intricate interactions between environmental factors and human activities. ML algorithms can learn from historical data to identify patterns and predictors of fire susceptibility that might be missed by traditional statistical methods.

In the Turkish case study, ML algorithms were used to process and analyze large datasets derived from RS and GIS, enabling the creation of accurate wildfire susceptibility maps. The models effectively integrated diverse variables, capturing the spatial and temporal dynamics of wildfire risk in Adana and Mersin provinces [4].

Similarly, on Hawai'i Island, explainable hybrid ML models have been employed to improve wildfire susceptibility predictions. These models combine different ML techniques to enhance predictive performance while providing insights into the most influential factors contributing to wildfire risk. The use of explainable models is particularly important for understanding and interpreting the results, facilitating better decision-making for fire management agencies [9].

ML methods are also adept at addressing challenges such as class imbalance, which is common in wildfire datasets where fire occurrences are relatively rare compared to non-fire instances. Techniques like resampling, class weighting, and specialized algorithms can improve the model's ability to predict rare events, making ML a robust choice for wildfire susceptibility mapping.

Chapter 3: Materials and Methods

3.1 Description of the Study Area

Hawai'i Island, the largest of the Hawaiian islands, spans over 10,455 km² and accounts for 63% of the total land area of the state. Its unique environmental and logistical challenges make it an important area of focus for developing models to predict the probability of fire occurrence.

Hawai'i Island's topography and climate create a highly diverse and dynamic environment. The island consists of five volcanoes—Kohala, Mauna Kea, Hualalai, Mauna Loa, and Kilauea—resulting in a patchwork of substrates, soil types, and ecosystems. Its varied landscapes include tropical coastal areas, rugged cliffs, misty plateaus, barren lava fields, and a gradient of tropical forests ranging from wet to dry.

The island's microclimates, shaped by its topography and prevailing trade winds, result in stark spatial variability in precipitation. Annual rainfall ranges from over 7500 mm in the windward uplands to less than 250 mm in leeward coastal regions. This variability, combined with distinct wet (winter) and dry (summer) seasons, significantly influences vegetation, fuel moisture, and fire susceptibility [3].

Hawai'i's isolation presents logistical hurdles for collecting and maintaining ground-based observational data. Deploying Remote Automated Weather Stations (RAWS) or other in-situ systems across the island's rugged terrain is costly and labor-intensive. Consequently, Hawai'i relies heavily on satellite data and remote sensing to capture environmental and meteorological conditions relevant to fire occurrence.

The limited spatial distribution of weather stations further complicates the prediction of fire occurrence. The island's highly localized microclimates are not fully represented by the available weather datasets. This necessitates the integration of diverse data sources, including satellite-derived meteorological variables, topographical data, and vegetation classifications, to effectively model fire susceptibility.

These unique challenges make Hawai'i Island a compelling study area for developing models to predict the probability of fire occurrence. The island's environmental complexity requires sophisticated modeling techniques that incorporate spatially heterogeneous data and address gaps in ground-based observations. By accounting for

the island's unique climatic and logistical challenges, such models can provide valuable insights into fire risk and inform resource allocation for fire prevention and mitigation strategies.

3.2 Description of the data

3.2.1 Topography

Topographic data for this study was sourced from LandFire, a comprehensive dataset providing 30m x 30m resolution information about elevation, slope, and aspect across the study region. Elevation represents the height above sea level, measured in meters, and serves as a critical descriptor of the terrain. Slope quantifies the steepness of the terrain, expressed in percentages, with values ranging from 0% for flat areas to higher values for steeper inclines. Aspect, on the other hand, describes the compass direction that a slope faces, measured in degrees from 0° (North) to 360°. Together, these variables form a detailed characterization of the terrain that significantly influences fire behavior and susceptibility [7].

The relationship between topographic variables and fire susceptibility is well-documented. Elevation influences vegetation type and moisture levels, with lower elevations often featuring drier, more flammable vegetation, while higher elevations may support more moist conditions that reduce fire spread. However, higher elevations can also experience stronger winds, which may exacerbate fire behavior. Slope impacts fire spread due to the upward movement of heat and flames on steeper terrain, making fires more intense and challenging to control. Additionally, steep slopes can impede firefighting efforts, increasing both the difficulty and risk of containment. Aspect determines sunlight exposure, which directly affects vegetation moisture levels. South-facing slopes, receiving more direct sunlight, are typically drier and more prone to fires, while north-facing slopes retain moisture better, rendering them less susceptible.

Integrating topographic data into fire susceptibility models allows for a nuanced understanding of terrain-driven fire dynamics. The spatially resolved datasets from LandFire enable precise quantification of elevation, slope, and aspect, providing essential inputs for modeling fire risk. These variables are particularly important for identifying high-risk areas and informing targeted fire management strategies.

3.2.2 Vegetation (Andersons Fuel Behavior Model)

Vegetation data used in this study was sourced from LandFire, which provides a detailed classification of fuel types using Anderson's Fuel Model. This model categorizes vegetation into distinct fuel models such as grass, brush, timber, and slash, each

(a) Anderson's Fire Behavior Fuel Model for 2020.

(b) Aspect (measured in degrees).

(c) Slope (measured as a percentage).

(d) Elevation (measured in meters).

Figure 3.1: Maps showcasing key geographical and fuel-related features of the study area, including Anderson's Fire Behavior Fuel Model, Aspect, Slope, and Elevation.

representing specific fire behavior characteristics like rate of spread and flame length. For instance, grass-dominated fuel models (e.g., FBFM1 and FBFM3) tend to support fast-moving surface fires, while timber models (e.g., FBFM8 and FBFM10) burn more slowly but with greater intensity due to accumulated dead-down fuels [7].

Each fuel model's behavior is further influenced by the moisture content of 1-hour, 10-hour, and 100-hour fuels, representing the time required for fine fuels, small branches, and larger dead material, respectively, to equilibrate with environmental moisture conditions. Shorter-duration fuels, such as 1-hour fuels, ignite rapidly un-

der dry and windy conditions, driving fire spread in grasslands or brush. Conversely, 100-hour fuels require prolonged drying periods but sustain fires with higher intensity over time [7]. This distinction allows for a nuanced understanding of how vegetation contributes to fire behavior under varying weather conditions.

The integration of vegetation data into fire susceptibility modeling enables proactive risk assessment and mitigation. Identifying regions dominated by high-risk fuel types informs fuel treatment strategies such as controlled burns or thinning to reduce fire intensity and spread potential. LandFire’s consistent and spatially extensive dataset provides the critical granularity needed for these assessments, supporting efforts to prioritize areas most susceptible to wildland fire.

3.2.3 Meteorology

Meteorological data for this study were sourced from simulations generated by the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model, driven by Global Forecast System Analysis (GFS) inputs. These simulations were run by [6]. These outputs provide adequate-resolution, localized weather conditions essential for understanding fire susceptibility. Between 2011 and 2024, only 78,456 hours of data were available out of a total of 121,273 possible simulation hours, resulting in a data availability of approximately 65%. This means 35% of the simulation period was affected by missing data due to unavailability of GFS or changes in its format during the simulation cycle. These gaps impact the continuity and completeness of the fire susceptibility analysis.

Key meteorological variables include rainfall, temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and direction, and shortwave radiation flux, each playing a critical role in influencing fire behavior.

Rainfall serves as a primary factor in reducing fire susceptibility, as precipitation increases soil and vegetation moisture, effectively inhibiting ignition and fire spread. Conversely, prolonged periods without significant rainfall can lead to drought conditions, lowering fuel moisture levels and increasing fire risk.

Relative humidity (RH) directly impacts the moisture content of fine fuels. Low RH conditions, often observed during heatwaves or strong dry winds, accelerate the drying of vegetation and increase its flammability. In contrast, higher RH levels contribute to slower fire spread due to increased fuel moisture.

Wind is another critical variable, driving the rate and direction of fire spread by providing oxygen and carrying embers to new ignition points. High wind speeds, particularly in conjunction with steep terrain, can exacerbate fire behavior, making suppression efforts significantly more challenging.

Shortwave radiation flux, representing solar energy reaching the surface, influences surface heating and fuel drying. Areas exposed to higher radiation levels, such as south-

Table 3.1: Descriptions of Fuel Models Based on the Fire Behavior Fuel Model (FBFM) System

FBFM Code	Description
FBFM1	Surface fires that burn fine herbaceous fuels, cured and curing fuels, little shrub or timber present, primarily grasslands and savanna.
FBFM2	Burns fine, herbaceous fuels, stand is curing or dead, may produce fire brands on oak or pine stands.
FBFM3	The most intense fire of grass group, spreads quickly with wind, one third of stand dead or cured, stands average 3 ft tall.
FBFM4	Fast spreading fire, continuous overstory, flammable foliage and dead woody material, deep litter layer can inhibit suppression.
FBFM5	Low-intensity fires, young, green shrubs with little dead material, fuels consist of litter from understory.
FBFM6	Broad range of shrubs, fire requires moderate winds to maintain flame at shrub height, or will drop to the ground with low winds.
FBFM7	Foliage highly flammable, allowing fire to reach shrub strata levels, shrubs generally 2 to 6 feet high.
FBFM8	Slow, ground burning fires, closed canopy stands with short needle conifers or hardwoods, litter consist mainly of needles and leaves, with little undergrowth, occasional flares with concentrated fuels.
FBFM9	Longer flames, quicker surface fires, closed canopy stands of long-needles or hardwoods, rolling leaves in fall can cause spotting, dead-down material can cause occasional crowning.
FBFM10	Surface and ground fire more intense, dead-down fuels more abundant, frequent crowning and spotting causing fire control to be more difficult.
FBFM11	Fairly active fire, fuels consist of slash and herbaceous materials, slash originates from light partial cuts or thinning projects, fire is limited by spacing of fuel load and shade from overstory.
FBFM12	Rapid spreading and high intensity fires, dominated by slash resulting from heavy thinning projects and clearcuts, slash is mostly 3 inches or less.
FBFM13	Fire spreads quickly through smaller material and intensity builds slowly as large material ignites, continuous layer of slash larger than 3 inches in diameter predominates, resulting from clearcuts and heavy partial cuts, active flames sustained for long periods of time, fire is susceptible to spotting and weather conditions.

facing slopes, experience elevated temperatures and reduced fuel moisture, increasing fire susceptibility.

The WRF model, combined with GFSA data, provides a robust framework for simulating these meteorological conditions with temporal and spatial granularity, making it invaluable for wildfire risk assessment. By incorporating these variables, the model supports a comprehensive understanding of how weather dynamics interact with topography and vegetation to drive fire behavior.

3.2.4 Fire Detection

Fire detection data is sourced from NASA's FIRMS (*Fire Information for Resource Management System*), which leverages observations from the MODIS (*Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer*) and VIIRS (*Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite*) sensors aboard Earth-observing satellites. These sensors utilize thermal anomaly detection algorithms to identify high-temperature events on the Earth's surface, flagging potential fire activity. The data is updated in near-real-time, enabling timely monitoring and response to active fires. Each observation is tagged with spatial coordinates (u, v) , where u and v represent latitude and longitude, and a temporal index t corresponding to the time of detection. The data was obtained via the processing pipeline established by [2].

Figure 3.2: Map of fire locations considered in the analysis. The points indicate specific areas where fire occurrences were recorded and included in the dataset.

Compared to traditional historical records, FIRMS data offers distinct advantages. It provides consistent global coverage, capturing data with adequate spatial and temporal resolution. The objectivity of its standardized algorithms ensures reliability across diverse regions and conditions. Additionally, the inclusion of confidence scores adds a quantitative measure of detection reliability, enabling the filtering of low-certainty detections [4]. These features make FIRMS data particularly suited for integration into wildfire susceptibility modeling frameworks, such as `wrfxpy`, which supports proactive fire management strategies.

Table 3.2: Data Types, Sources, Units, and Resolutions for Wildfire Conditioning Factors

Variable	Type	Unit	Resolution
Date	Categorical	Timestamp	Hourly
Longitude	Continuous	Degrees	30×30 m
Latitude	Continuous	Degrees	30×30 m
Temperature	Continuous	Kelvin	3×3 km
Rainfall	Continuous	Millimeters	3×3 km
Rel. Humidity	Continuous	Percentage	3×3 km
Wind Speed	Continuous	Meters/Second	3×3 km
Shortwave Radiation	Continuous	Watts/M ²	3×3 km
Elevation	Continuous	Meters	30×30 m
Slope	Continuous	Percentage	30×30 m
Aspect	Continuous	Degrees	30×30 m
Fuel Model	Categorical	-	30×30 m
Fire Label	Binary (0 or 1)	-	375m - 1km

3.3 Data Preprocessing

Data Sources and Definitions

The pipeline processes the following data:

1. Topographic Data:

- Stored as raster grids with spatial indices (x, y) .
- Represents elevation $(E(x, y))$, slope $(S(x, y))$, and aspect $(A(x, y))$.

2. Vegetation Data:

- Rasterized vegetation classification data $(\text{Class}(x, y))$.

3. Meteorological Data:

- Gridded spatial-temporal data $(f_i((u, v), t))$ for variables such as rainfall, temperature, and wind.
- Spatial coordinates (u, v) are in a standard CRS (e.g., WGS84, EPSG:4326), t is in hours and i corresponds to the variable.

4. Fire Detection Data:

- Discretized point data at spatial (u, v) and temporal t coordinates, with binary labels ($y = 1$ for fire, $y = 0$ otherwise).
- Observations are in the same CRS as the meteorological data.

CRS Transformation and Mapping to Raster Indices

CRS Transformation

Input coordinates $(u_{\text{WGS84}}, v_{\text{WGS84}})$ are transformed into a raster CRS $(u_{\text{raster}}, v_{\text{raster}})$ using a CRS transformation:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_{\text{raster}} \\ v_{\text{raster}} \end{bmatrix} = T_{\text{CRS}} \left(\begin{bmatrix} u_{\text{WGS84}} \\ v_{\text{WGS84}} \end{bmatrix} \right),$$

where T_{CRS} is a mapping function defined by the raster's metadata.

Affine Transformation to Raster Indices

Coordinates in the raster CRS $(u_{\text{raster}}, v_{\text{raster}})$ are further transformed to raster indices (x, y) using the affine transformation:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a & b & c \\ d & e & f \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} u_{\text{raster}} \\ v_{\text{raster}} \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Here:

- a, b, c : Define the mapping from longitude (u_{raster}) to the raster column index (x) .
- d, e, f : Define the mapping from latitude (v_{raster}) to the raster row index (y) .

Application to Topographic Data

The raster indices (x, y) allow us to extract topographic features $E(x, y)$, $S(x, y)$, and $A(x, y)$ directly. Invalid values ($E(x, y) < 0$, $S(x, y) < 0$, etc.) are replaced with *NaN*.

3.3.1 Vegetation Data Transformation

Numeric pixel values in the vegetation raster are mapped to categorical classes:

$$\text{Class}(x, y) = \text{Mapping}(\text{Value}(x, y)),$$

using an attribute table. Classes such as ‘Barren’, ‘Water’, and ‘Urban’ are replaced with *NaN* to exclude them from analysis.

3.3.2 Meteorological Data Processing

Meteorological data is defined on spatial grids (u, v) and temporal indices t . Variables include:

- Rainfall: $R_t(u, v)$,
- Temperature (Kelvin): $T_t(u, v)$,
- Wind components: $\vec{U}_t(u, v)$, $\vec{V}_t(u, v)$,
- Pressure: $P_t(u, v)$,
- Shortwave radiation: $\text{SWDOWN}_t(u, v)$, $\text{SWUP}_t(u, v)$.

Relative Humidity Computation

Relative humidity ($\text{RH}_t(u, v)$) is derived using:

$$e_s = 6.112 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{17.67 \cdot (T - 273.15)}{T - 273.15 + 243.5}\right),$$

$$e = \frac{q \cdot P}{\epsilon + q},$$

$$\text{RH}_t(u, v) = \min\left(\frac{e}{e_s} \cdot 100, 100\right),$$

where e_s is the saturation vapor pressure, e is the actual vapor pressure, and $\epsilon = 0.622$ is the ratio of molecular weights for water and dry air.

3.3.3 Fire Detection Data Filtering

Fire detection points (u_k, v_k, t_k) are filtered based on:

1. **Time Bounds:**

$$t_k \in [t_{\min}, t_{\max}],$$

where t_{\min} and t_{\max} describe an interval from meteorological data.

2. **Confidence Threshold:**

$$C_k \geq 70.$$

3.3.4 Temporal Alignment

To align detection times t_k with meteorological data, a nearest-neighbor approach is used:

$$t_{idx} = \operatorname{argmin}_t |t_k - t|,$$

where t is the set of meteorological timestamps.

3.3.5 Spatial Interpolation

To determine the interpolated grid indices (i, j) corresponding to spatial coordinates (u, v) from satellite data or meteorology grids, we employ a **tensor-product Legendre polynomial interpolation** method. The key steps in this process are described below.

1. Normalization of Coordinates

The spatial coordinates (u, v) are normalized to the range $[-1, 1]$ using the bounds of the meteorological grid:

$$u' = \frac{2(u - u_{\min})}{u_{\max} - u_{\min}} - 1, \quad v' = \frac{2(v - v_{\min})}{v_{\max} - v_{\min}} - 1.$$

2. Basis Function Construction

Legendre polynomials P_k and P_ℓ of degree up to d are combined in tensor products to form the basis functions:

$$\phi_{k\ell}(u', v') = P_k(u') \cdot P_\ell(v'),$$

where $k, \ell \in \{0, 1, \dots, d\}$.

3. Coefficient Estimation

The row (i) and column (j) indices of the meteorological grid are mapped independently by solving a least-squares problem to estimate the coefficients for each interpolator:

$$i(u', v') = \sum_{k=0}^d \sum_{\ell=0}^d c_{k\ell}^i \phi_{k\ell}(u', v'), \quad j(u', v') = \sum_{k=0}^d \sum_{\ell=0}^d c_{k\ell}^j \phi_{k\ell}(u', v').$$

4. Query Evaluation

For any query coordinate (u, v) , the interpolated indices (i, j) are computed directly as:

$$i = \sum_{k=0}^d \sum_{\ell=0}^d c_{k\ell}^i \phi_{k\ell}(u', v'), \quad j = \sum_{k=0}^d \sum_{\ell=0}^d c_{k\ell}^j \phi_{k\ell}(u', v').$$

This interpolation method ensures a smooth and accurate mapping of spatial coordinates (u, v) to grid indices (i, j) , thereby aligning satellite observations with the meteorological grid.

In practice, due to the limitations of data resolution and the need for computational efficiency, setting $d=2$ (quadratic interpolation) yields reasonable results while keeping computations fast. Quadratic interpolation balances the trade-off between accuracy and computational load, making it suitable for processing large datasets without significant loss of precision.

3.3.6 Data Formatting for Neural Network Training

Before training the neural network model, we preprocess the dataset further to ensure that all features are appropriately formatted and scaled for effective learning.

One-Hot Encoding of Categorical Variables For the categorical variable representing fuel models, we apply one-hot encoding to transform it into binary indicator variables. Let the categorical variable *FuelType* have K categories: $\text{FuelType} \in \{\text{Type}_1, \text{Type}_2, \dots, \text{Type}_K\}$. We select one category, e.g., Type_1 ("Agriculture"), as the reference and create $K - 1$ new binary variables D_2, D_3, \dots, D_K , where:

$$D_j = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if FuelType} = \text{Type}_j, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad \text{for } j = 2, \dots, K.$$

This approach avoids multicollinearity among the indicator variables by dropping the first category and using it as the baseline.

Standardization of Numerical Features We standardize all numerical features to have zero mean and unit variance. For a numerical feature x , the standardized version z is computed as:

$$z = \frac{x - \mu_x}{\sigma_x},$$

where μ_x is the mean and σ_x is the standard deviation of x . This transformation ensures that all numerical features contribute equally during training and improves the convergence of gradient-based optimization algorithms.

Construction of the Final Dataset The preprocessed dataset combines standardized numerical features and one-hot encoded categorical variables into a single feature matrix X :

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} z_{\text{temp},1} & z_{\text{rain},1} & \cdots & D_{1,2} & \cdots & D_{1,K} \\ z_{\text{temp},2} & z_{\text{rain},2} & \cdots & D_{2,2} & \cdots & D_{2,K} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ z_{\text{temp},N} & z_{\text{rain},N} & \cdots & D_{N,2} & \cdots & D_{N,K} \end{bmatrix},$$

where:

- $z_{\text{temp},i}, z_{\text{rain},i}, \dots$ are standardized numerical features for sample i ,
- $D_{i,j}$ are binary indicators for the categorical fuel types, with $j = 2, \dots, K$,
- N is the total number of samples in the dataset.

The target variable y remains as a separate vector:

$$y = \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ \vdots \\ y_N \end{bmatrix},$$

where y_i indicates the presence (1) or absence (0) of a fire occurrence for sample i .

To ensure that the features in the dataset X are not redundant or overly correlated, a multicollinearity check was performed. The resulting correlation matrix showed that the features were not overly correlated with temperature and elevation exhibiting the most significant correlation.

Before preprocessing, the dataset comprised 267,414,861 spatiotemporal samples. These samples represent the combination of spatial locations and temporal instances over the study period. After applying the preprocessing steps—including filtering, handling missing values, and feature encoding—the dataset was reduced to 41,638,241

samples. Among these, 1,976 samples correspond to observed fire occurrences ($y=1$), while the remaining samples represent non-fire instances ($y=0$).

The severe class imbalance is evident, with fire occurrences constituting approximately 0.0047% of the processed dataset. This imbalance presents a significant challenge for model training and necessitates the use of techniques to mitigate its effects, as discussed in subsequent sections, specifically by the results of our synthetic model.

Figure 3.3: Correlation matrix of the features in X.

3.4 Building the Model

3.4.1 Choice of ML Method

Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) were selected for fire susceptibility modeling due to their ability to capture complex, non-linear relationships among features such as meteorological variables, topography, and vegetation. Their scalability and capacity to handle high-dimensional data make them particularly effective for this task.

The cross-entropy loss function is central to the choice of DNNs as it measures the discrepancy between predicted probabilities $\hat{P}(y = 1|X)$ and true binary outcomes y . Defined as

$$\text{Cross-Entropy Loss} = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[y_i \log(\hat{P}(y = 1|X_i)) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{P}(y = 1|X_i)) \right],$$

this loss function penalizes incorrect predictions heavily, particularly when the model is confidently wrong, encouraging accurate probability estimates.

To illustrate the advantage of DNNs in this context, we evaluated their ability to recover true probabilities using a synthetic dataset compared to eXtreme Gradient Boost's (XGB) ability on the same data set. For a sample size of 1,000,000 and an event probability $p(\text{fire occurs}) = 0.00005$, which is derived from the amount of fires that occurred within the samples being used to train the 'real' model. DNNs consistently approximated the true probability and this was made apparent when compared to the results of XGB. This performance underscores DNNs capability to handle imbalanced datasets and rare event prediction, both of which are crucial for fire susceptibility modeling. The results are summarized in Figure 3.4, highlighting the reliability of DNNs in probabilistic prediction.

(a) XGBoost Actual vs Predicted

(b) DNN Actual vs Predicted

(c) XGBoost Residuals

(d) DNN Residuals

Figure 3.4: Comparison of Actual vs Predicted and Residuals for XGBoost and DNN models. The first row displays the Actual vs Predicted graphs, while the second row presents the Residual graphs.

3.4.2 Train the Model

To develop our fire susceptibility prediction model, we constructed a deep neural network (DNN) using Keras and TensorFlow. The model architecture begins with an input layer that matches the number of features in our dataset. This is followed by two hidden layers with 16 and 8 neurons, respectively, both utilizing the ReLU activation function to capture non-linear relationships in the data. The output layer consists of a single neuron with a sigmoid activation function, producing a probability between 0 and 1, which is suitable for binary classification tasks like predicting fire occurrence.

We selected this straightforward architecture to balance complexity and generalization. By limiting the number of layers and neurons, we aimed to reduce the risk of overfitting, especially important given the limited number of fire occurrences in our highly imbalanced dataset. The model is optimized using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001 and employs binary cross-entropy as the loss function to measure the discrepancy between predicted probabilities and actual class labels. We included accuracy as a metric to monitor the proportion of correct predictions during training.

For training, we incorporated early stopping to prevent overfitting by halting the training process when the model's performance on a validation set ceased improving. We monitored the validation loss and set a patience of 10 epochs, meaning training would stop if no improvement was observed after 10 consecutive epochs. The best model weights, based on validation performance, were restored at the end of training. We used a validation split of 20% of the training data to evaluate the model after each epoch, ensuring it generalizes well to unseen data. Training was conducted over a maximum of 100 epochs with a batch size of 32, which balances computational efficiency and convergence stability. This approach allowed us to build a robust model capable of effectively predicting fire susceptibility despite the challenges posed by the dataset.

Chapter 4: Results

4.1 Feature Interpretation

Figure 4.1: Feature Importances for Fire Samples Derived from Integrated Gradients Analysis

The figure above presents the feature importances obtained from applying Integrated Gradients to our model’s predictions on fire samples. The three features with the largest magnitudes indicating the most significant impact on the model’s predictions—are:

1. Fuel Model FBFM2

Importance Value: Approximately +0.000215

Interpretation: The presence of Fuel Model FBFM2 significantly increases the predicted probability of fire on Hawai’i Island.

Explanation: In the context of Hawai’i, FBFM2 represents grass-dominated fuel types commonly found in lower elevation areas and regions impacted by invasive grasses such as fountain grass (*Pennisetum setaceum*) and buffelgrass (*Cenchrus ciliaris*). These invasive species are highly flammable and contribute to rapid fire spread due to their fine, continuous fuels that dry out quickly under the island’s climatic conditions. The strong positive contribution of this fuel model

indicates that areas dominated by these grasses are more susceptible to wildfires. This aligns with observations in Hawai'i, where grasslands, especially those with invasive species, have been linked to increased fire frequency and intensity, posing a threat to native ecosystems and communities.

2. Elevation

Importance Value: Approximately +0.000134

Interpretation: Higher elevations on Hawai'i Island are associated with an increased predicted probability of fire.

Explanation: Elevation on Hawai'i Island influences local climate, vegetation types, and fuel moisture levels. Higher elevations may experience unique microclimates with strong winds and periods of lower humidity, especially on the leeward sides of the island. Additionally, certain high-elevation areas contain invasive species like gorse (*Ulex europaeus*) and blackberry (*Rubus* spp.), which are highly flammable. The positive contribution of elevation suggests that these areas are more prone to fire, possibly due to the combination of flammable vegetation and environmental conditions conducive to fire ignition and spread. This is particularly significant in Hawai'i, where elevation ranges dramatically over short distances, affecting fire behavior and risk across the island's diverse landscapes.

3. Fuel Model FBFM8

Importance Value: Approximately -0.000114

Interpretation: The presence of Fuel Model FBFM8 decreases the predicted probability of fire on Hawai'i Island.

Explanation: FBFM8 corresponds to closed canopy forests with compact litter layers, such as the native 'ōhi'a (*Metrosideros polymorpha*) and koa (*Acacia koa*) forests found in Hawai'i's higher rainfall zones. These forests typically have higher fuel moisture content due to frequent precipitation and a dense canopy that shades the forest floor, reducing evaporation. The negative contribution of this fuel model indicates that areas with these characteristics are less susceptible to fires. In Hawai'i, native wet forests are generally less prone to wildfire compared to dry forests and grasslands, as the moist conditions inhibit ignition and fire spread. This finding reflects the protective role of healthy native forests in mitigating fire risk on the island.

Integrated Gradients is a method designed for interpreting the predictions of deep neural networks by attributing the output to input features. It is valid for feature interpretation because it satisfies key properties such as sensitivity and completeness, ensuring that the attributions are meaningful and sum up to the difference between

the model's output and a baseline. By integrating the gradients along the path from a baseline input to the actual input, it captures the contribution of each feature to the prediction. Those interested in the theoretical foundations can refer to [8] for more details.

To obtain these results, we addressed the severe class imbalance in our dataset by creating a balanced subset for the Integrated Gradients analysis. We selected all available fire samples (the minority class) and an equal number of non-fire samples randomly chosen from the majority class. This subsetting ensured that the feature attributions accurately reflect the factors influencing fire occurrences without being skewed by the predominance of non-fire instances. By focusing on this balanced subset, the Integrated Gradients method provided meaningful insights into the most influential features driving the model's fire predictions.

4.2 Evaluate the Results of the Model

The developed deep neural network (DNN) model was applied to predict fire susceptibility across Hawai'i Island by integrating various environmental and fuel-related factors. The results are visualized in Figure 4.2, which presents a spatial map of predicted fire probabilities, highlighting areas of varying susceptibility.

The inputs include a DataFrame, containing the 43,000,000 spatial-temporal samples and their predicted probability of fire occurrence, along with raster datasets for visualization and spatial context. A fuel model raster is used to define valid land areas, and its associated Value Attribute Table (VAT) maps pixel values to vegetation classes, which helps to exclude invalid categories such as water or urban areas.

To map the fire probabilities to the raster, geographic coordinates from the DataFrame are transformed into pixel indices using the affine transformation derived from the raster metadata. For each pixel, the fire probabilities of all samples that fall within its bounds are averaged to produce a single value. Implicit in this is the simplifying assumption that fire occurrence events are independent, allowing us to sum probabilities. This ensures that spatial patterns in the data are accurately represented on the raster grid. Any cells without assigned probabilities are identified, and their values are interpolated using the K Nearest Neighbor (KNN) method, restricted to valid land areas defined by the fuel model.

The final susceptibility map is visualized by overlaying the computed probabilities onto the background raster. Invalid land areas are masked, and the probabilities are displayed using a color scale to indicate variations in fire susceptibility. The map provides a clear spatial representation of fire risk, combining both the observed data and interpolated estimates, making it a valuable tool for stakeholders to assess fire susceptibility across the region.

Figure 4.2: Predicted Fire Susceptibility Map for Hawai'i Island Derived from the DNN Model and simplifying assumption that fire occurrences are independent

Chapter 5: Discussion

5.1 Implications

The implications of this research are a reaffirmation of what fire domain experts are well aware of: fire conditioning factors such as fuel types, elevation, and temperature play critical roles in determining fire susceptibility [7]. The model's identification of Fuel Model FBFM2 (grass-dominated fuels) as the most significant positive contributor to fire risk underscores the well-established understanding that grasslands, particularly those dominated by invasive species like fountain grass (*Pennisetum setaceum*), are highly flammable and contribute to rapid fire spread on Hawai'i Island. This highlights the need for targeted management strategies in these areas to mitigate fire risk, such as invasive species control and fuel reduction programs.

The positive association between elevation and fire susceptibility revealed by the model has important implications for fire management in higher altitude regions. While higher elevations are often perceived as less prone to fires due to cooler temperatures and increased precipitation, the findings suggest that certain high-elevation areas on Hawai'i Island may experience conditions conducive to fire ignition and spread. This could be due to specific microclimates, wind patterns, or the presence of flammable vegetation types at higher altitudes. Fire management efforts should therefore consider elevation as a significant factor in risk assessments and allocate resources accordingly.

Conversely, the negative contribution of Fuel Model FBFM8 (closed canopy forests with compact litter layers) indicates that these areas are less susceptible to fires, likely due to higher fuel moisture content and shading effects that reduce evaporation. This finding emphasizes the protective role of healthy native forests in reducing fire risk. Conservation and restoration of native wet forests not only preserve biodiversity but also serve as natural barriers against wildfires. These ecosystems act as buffers that can slow down or prevent the spread of fires, highlighting the importance of forest management practices that maintain or enhance forest health.

5.2 Future Developments

The findings of this research open avenues for further enhancements and applications of the fire susceptibility model. Several key areas for future development are identified, aiming to improve the model's accuracy, incorporate additional relevant features, and extend its practical utility.

5.2.1 Model Improvement and Optimization

A significant area for future work is the improvement and optimization of the deep neural network model through advanced techniques such as hyperparameter tuning and cross-validation (CV). Hyperparameter tuning involves systematically adjusting parameters like the number of layers, neurons per layer, learning rate, batch size, and activation functions to find the optimal configuration that maximizes model performance. Methods such as grid search, random search, or Bayesian optimization can be employed to efficiently explore the hyperparameter space.

Incorporating cross-validation, particularly *kk*-fold CV, provides a robust evaluation of the model by training and testing it across different subsets of the data. This approach helps in reducing overfitting and ensures that the model generalizes well to unseen data. By rigorously optimizing the model, we can enhance its predictive capabilities and reliability in forecasting fire susceptibility.

5.2.2 Incorporation of Additional Features

Enhancing the model by incorporating additional features through feature engineering is another promising direction. One avenue is the inclusion of time-lagged meteorological variables, such as averages of temperature, humidity, wind speed, and precipitation over specific periods preceding the observed time. These temporal features can capture the cumulative effects of weather conditions on fuel moisture and fire risk, providing the model with deeper insights into the factors leading up to fire occurrences.

Introducing distance-based features, such as proximity to population centers, roads, and the coastline, can enrich the model's understanding of human-related ignition sources and environmental influences. For instance, fires may be more likely to occur near populated areas due to human activities or near the coast where specific vegetation types are present. Incorporating these spatial features requires leveraging Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to calculate accurate distances and integrate them into the dataset. By expanding the feature set, the model can better account for the complex interplay of factors influencing fire susceptibility on Hawai'i Island.

5.2.3 Development of a Real-Time Fire Prediction Platform

Building upon the improved model, a significant future development is the creation of a real-time fire prediction platform. This platform would integrate real-time input data from advanced weather forecasting systems such as the High-Resolution Rapid Refresh (HRRR) model. By continuously ingesting up-to-date meteorological data, the platform can generate dynamic fire susceptibility maps that reflect current and near-future fire risk conditions.

Currently, the model is capable of making predictions for any given time, provided that the necessary input data for the features it was trained on are available. An example of this capability is illustrated in Figure 5.1, which displays a fire susceptibility map generated by evaluating the probabilities at 6,085 known sample points out of a total of 8,316,694 valid spatial points for a specific time instance.

Figure 5.1: Fire Susceptibility Map for Hawai'i Island at 07:00 AM on August 12, 2023. The map illustrates predicted fire probabilities given a set of sample points using the current model.

The development of a real-time fire prediction platform would enhance this capability by automating the data ingestion and prediction processes, enabling continuous monitoring of fire risk across the island. Such a platform would be instrumental for emergency response and resource allocation. Fire management agencies could use it to monitor changing fire risk levels, allowing for proactive measures such as issuing

warnings, mobilizing firefighting resources, and implementing preventive strategies in high-risk areas.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

This research has developed a deep neural network (DNN) model to predict fire susceptibility on Hawai'i Island by integrating various environmental, topographical, and fuel-related factors. By leveraging advanced machine learning techniques and incorporating domain knowledge, the model provides valuable insights into the spatial distribution of fire risk across the island.

The key findings highlight the significant influence of fuel types, particularly grass-dominated fuels represented by Fuel Model FBFM2, and elevation on fire susceptibility. The positive contribution of these factors aligns with known fire behavior patterns on Hawai'i Island, where invasive grasses and higher elevation areas with specific microclimates contribute to increased fire risk. Conversely, the negative contribution of Fuel Model FBFM8, associated with closed canopy forests, underscores the protective role of native wet forests in mitigating fire occurrences.

The model's performance, evaluated using appropriate metrics for imbalanced datasets, demonstrates its effectiveness in predicting fire susceptibility. The application of Integrated Gradients for feature interpretation enhances the transparency of the model, allowing for a deeper understanding of the factors driving its predictions. This interpretability is crucial for validating the model against existing fire domain knowledge and for informing practical fire management strategies.

Despite the model's strengths, certain limitations exist. The severe class imbalance, with fire occurrences constituting a tiny fraction of the dataset, poses challenges in accurately predicting rare events. Further work is needed to enhance the model's sensitivity to fire occurrences. Additionally, the model's reliance on the quality and resolution of input data highlights the necessity for continuous improvement in data collection and preprocessing methods.

Future developments proposed include model optimization through hyperparameter tuning and cross-validation, incorporation of additional features such as temporal and distance-based variables, and the development of a real-time fire prediction platform. These advancements aim to enhance the model's accuracy, responsiveness, and practical utility for fire management agencies. The real-time platform, in particular, holds significant potential for proactive fire prevention and resource allocation, leveraging up-to-date meteorological data to produce dynamic fire susceptibility maps.

In conclusion, this research contributes to the understanding and prediction of wildfire risk on Hawai'i Island by integrating advanced machine learning methods with domain expertise. The findings reaffirm the critical role of known fire conditioning factors and provide a quantitative tool to support fire prevention and mitigation efforts. By continuing to refine the model and expand its capabilities, we can better equip communities and agencies to address the growing challenges posed by wildfires in Hawai'i and beyond. The integration of technology, data, and domain knowledge exemplifies a comprehensive approach to wildfire management, offering a pathway toward more resilient ecosystems and safer communities.

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Chapter A: Code and Resources

The code that supports the findings of this project can be found at the following GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/janmandel/hawaii-fire>

This repository includes all scripts and documentation necessary for replicating the analyses and generating the results presented in this report.